

D3.02 Recommendations for GEP Report

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GEARING ROLES project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that brings together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned in designing, implementing, and evaluating six Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training in these areas, mentoring activities, awareness raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ETAg	Eesti Teadusagentuur (Estonian Research Council)
E-UC	End-User Community
FF UL	Filozofska fakulteta//Faculty of Arts University of Ljubljana
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GR	GEARING-Roles
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IGOT UL	Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento do Território, Universidade de Lisboa
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
OBU	Oxford Brookes University
PGAs	Participatory Gender Audits
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
SU	Sabancı Üniversitesi
UDEUSTO	Universidad de Deusto
WP	Work Package
YW	Yellow Window

1. Introduction and background

D3.2. Recommendations for GEP report draws on the work previously conducted and elaborated in D3.1. It is an outcome of the different, intertwined processes and tasks of WP3. Tasks 3.1 (Contextual analyses of legal and cultural practices at the macro level), 3.2. (Collection of gender equality-relevant data at the institutional level), 3.3. (Comparison of gender inequality across disciplines) and 3.4. (Self-diagnosis through Participatory Gender Audits, PGAs) were the basis for outlining the WP3 main working document, WP3 Guidelines for contextual analyses and institutional baseline assessment (Guidelines).

Following the Guidelines, six GEP implementing institutions (Oxford Brookes University, UK (from hereon OBU); Sabanci University, Turkey (from hereon SU); University of Deusto, Spain (from hereon UDEUSTO); Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento do Territorio at the University of Lisbon, Portugal (from here on IGOT); Filozofska fakulteta, at the University of Ljubljana, Slovenia (from here on UL FF); and Eesti Teadusagentuur, Estonian Research Council (from here on ETAg)), performed institutional baseline assessments, based on which the institutions concluded the analyses with self-diagnoses.

This self-diagnosis was summarized in the concluding part of the institutional baseline assessment report. Six GEP implementing institutions were asked to summarize the findings in such a way that the summaries themselves already provided topics for planning PGAs and also provided a first step in the institutional self-diagnosis process (task 3.4.) and the first step in planning and discussing possible actions for GEPs.

The institutions were then also asked to perform PGAs, based on the prior training, held by Yellow Window (YW) experts at Oxford Brookes University in June 2019. YW trainers presented a few possible approaches to PGAs from which institutions could draw and adapt to their own institutional purposes and needs. In this light, no additional guidelines were given on how to structure and perform PGAs. Nevertheless, institutional assessment was needed beforehand in order to provide an important insight into resistance within the institutions. The decision was made to perform PGAs until October 2019. The six GEP implementing institutions were asked to write a short report on the PGAs performed, setting out the objectives, actors included, techniques used, conclusions, proposed action to be taken, limitations, resistance, etc. with the short summary as a self-diagnosis (which is to be used as the basis for a preliminary action plan for GEP). These reports were uploaded to the project platform HERMIONE, and the six implementing institutions as well as YW experts were asked to comment on possible points of improvement. The outcomes of PGAs were presented and discussed at the consortium meeting in Lisbon in November 2019 in order to provide each institution with appropriate feedback and recommendations for GEPs, (task 3.5.) which are included in the D3.2. Recommendations for GEP report.

The Recommendations for GEP report aims at providing GEP implementing institutions with additional insight, and a mapping of possible inspirations for the development of GEPs.

Taking into account institutional specifics, the chapters that follow provide institutions with guidance for their GEP preparation. The first section presents the institutional self-diagnoses, as presented in the institutional baseline assessments (part of D3.1), some common issues and the recommendations for GEPs, referring to existing tools and practices. The second part provides recommendations on the process and for the next steps.

2. Recommendations based on partners' self-assessments

2.1. Institutional self-diagnosing capabilities and action planning: Summary of conclusions from partners' self-assessments, including the institutional PGAs

According to the GR project initiative and in line with the recommendations of the European Commission, a set of actions for conducting institutional baseline assessments and participatory gender audits were undertaken as part of WP3. Following the recommendations put forth by the GEAR tool and SUPERA indicators that have been used for institutional baseline assessments as part of WP3, six GEP implementing institutions identified their gender gaps and reflected on possible areas of improvement of gender equality at the institutional level. The aim of these institutional self-recommendations is to provide individual institutions with an initial mapping of possible actions for their Gender Equality Plan.

Analysis of the six institutional baseline assessment reports shows that all six institutions demonstrate self-diagnostic abilities and capabilities for action planning. Three institutions, OBU, UDEUSTO and IGOT, also provide self-evaluations on the progress being made, since such institutional inquiries had already been made in the past. All six institutions share common concerns while keeping in mind institutional specifics. A common concern in the action planning of GEPs is a careful deliberation on the issues GEPs are going to tackle, keeping in mind possibilities and strategies for success. This can be addressed by using, for example, SMART objectives for assessing the GEP in terms of being specific, measurable, attainable, and relevant and time bound.

While in their institutional reports, six GEP implementing institutions have demonstrated the ability for self-identifying areas in gender equality but have not yet (with few minor exceptions) inquired into possible forms of institutional action. In this regard PGAs share the same logic. In addition to what has been reported in Deliverable D.3.1., PGAs mostly contributed to

ownership, forming institutional (common) understanding of gender equality and support in the process of GEP implementation. Areas of possible GEP identified in institutional baseline assessments have been communicated in different ways, using different participatory techniques with relevant stakeholders and target groups at the level of the institution, forming a common understanding and ownership, gender awareness and sensitivity, but have not yet proposed possible steps for institutional action.

2.1.1. Institutional self-diagnoses

The findings of the institutional baseline assessment reports and reports on PGAs at individual institutions overlap.

SU, in its summary of the institutional baseline report, outlines a number of possible areas of improvement, starting with the representation of women in the fields they are underrepresented¹. SU also puts forth another common issue that has to do with the prevalence of administrative staff and the question of transparency of recruitment and progression processes. SU also presents the need for systematic sex-disaggregated databases and monitoring the improvements as well as gender sensitivity in curricula. Addressing gender inequality beyond binary categories is on the list of possible gender-related issues to address at the institutional level, too, while gender-sensitive language protocols could also be suggested in terms of the equality measures to be implemented.

UL FF identifies five areas of possible action plans for their GEP. The possibility of establishing sex-disaggregated databases is at the top of its list, with some initial suggestions for action. Internal policies for a gender-sensitive work life balance are also suggested as a possible topic of further GEP planning. Gender equality is intended to be placed in the institutional mission documents and put as a goal in its program for further activities. Efforts for gender-sensitive language are to be continued. Gender-sensitive guidelines for curricula and research are to be taken into consideration, as well as raising awareness of and sensitivity towards gender sensitive issues.

IGOT notes the number of women in leadership positions is lower compared to man, and emphasizes the impact of national economic measures as a structuring element in gender inequality. Financial limitations at the national level inhibit hiring new teachers. This partly limits greater representation of women in academia as well as their progression within academia. The need for sex-disaggregated databases at the institutional level is put forth, similar to those institutions which have no such data. Databases are also recognized as an important starting point to revealing inequalities and tackling institutional biases in relation to

¹This is a common issue for all the institutions, and is especially related to women in STEM and leadership positions. IGOT, UDEUSTO, UL FF and ETAg also share this concern – while also having institutionally specific issues related to the representation of women.

work - life balance. Gender-sensitive curricula and protocols for prevention of sexual harassment are also noted as areas for possible improvement.

OBU and UDEUSTO provide some information in relation to institutional progress being made from the last such inquiry in the status of gender equality at the institutional level.

UDEUSTO stresses the importance of national regulations which oblige universities to carry out gender equality plans. This contributed to the establishment of institutional sex-disaggregated databases that enable gathering, monitoring and benchmarking UDEUSTOs progress in gender equality issues. This enabled it to compare and address cultural patterns in gender equality as one of the factors hindering institutional gender equality, which mainly have to do with women still being seen as the dominant caregivers. They also addressed educational and professional segregation a prevalence of women in academic staff at some faculties (SSH) as well as administrative services. They detected the need to increase efforts for the integration of a gender perspective in research and teaching, as well as tackle resistance to this in teacher training. UDEUSTO, like the other institutions, also problematizes the gender ratio of women in leadership and decision-making positions. The process of promotion to full professor at UDEUSTO is observed to be three times longer for women in comparison to men. A pay gap, similar to other institutions, occurs in the variable part of the salary. The need to increase women's participation in public events as well as continued efforts on establishing sexual harassment protocols remain issues to be resolved.

OBU's self diagnosis differs substantially from the others. It has to do with refinement of mechanisms in relation to various gender equality areas that have already been established. Nevertheless there are still efforts to attract women in leadership positions, and to help in their progression by providing mentoring programs for fully employed as well as part-time staff. Improvements in relation to the status of part time staff (also in terms of gender) are recognized as necessary. Family friendly policies and ensuring a good work-life balance are institutional commitments that OBU continues to pursue. Efforts to monitor data and increase the inclusiveness of leadership positions and curricula have highlighted the gender and intersectionality of BAME student and staff. OBU also presents the differences in working time of men and women as something to be explored further.

ETAg, as the only GEP implementing RFO in the project, leaves aside its internal gender imbalance (the share of women is significantly higher among the employees) and instead emphasizes the issue of lack of gender consciousness in awarding grants. It observes that the success rate for male applicants is higher and women are underrepresented in several categories of grants.

2.1.2. Common challenges

Some common issues can be identified in the majority of institutional self-assessments, and these are:

- The importance of institutional sex-disaggregated databases and the need to establishing these where data and information are scattered;
- The under-representation of women (teaching staff and researchers, students) in some disciplines, study programs and in the institutional management and over-representation in others;
- Scepticism towards gender quotas and affirmative action;
- Leadership and decision-making bodies are predominantly male;
- Horizontal gender pay gaps;
- Work-life balance appears to be a cultural issue, with shared responsibilities between national and institutional regulations;
- Gender inequalities in recruitment and progression criteria are detected;
- Formal mentorship/sponsorship for women at the beginning of their professional careers could be established to help promote young academics. Gender-sensitive curricula and gender content in research are still a “work in progress”;
- The need to strengthen gender equality through raising awareness about and tackling stereotypes, discrimination, and sexual harassment;
- The need for protocols to assure the equality of LGBT+ communities is identified.

2.2. Recommendations for GEPs

Despite a number of common issues concerning the preparation of GEPs, the possibilities of implementation are context specific. Keeping this in mind, the recommendations for GEPs that follow aim to provide implementing institutions with possible references which can help them in their efforts to plan and implement GEPs. Inspiration in preparing GEPs and also an example template² can be found in Target’s guidelines to customize GEPs.

Based on the common concerns identified in the institutional self-assessments and listed above, a general recommendation for all institutions preparing GEPs would be to explore the possibilities offered by the GEAR tool action toolbox³. Inspiration on how to tackle common as well as institutional specific issues (above) can be clustered in four basic areas of indicators, following the SUPERA tool:

- Recruitment, retention, career progression, and work-life balance;
- Leadership;

² http://www.gendertarget.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/741672_TARGET_D3.3-GEP-Guidelines.pdf

³ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear>

- Gender in research and knowledge transfer;
- Gender biases, sexism and sexual harassment.

In the table below, we have structured some relevant resources that can inspire GEP implementers to design their actions. These initiatives complement the guidelines provided in the GEAR tool⁴ for each of the areas of intervention and do not pretend to be exhaustive, but to provide some ideas about how to tackle the issues arising from the institutional reports.

Table 1: Relevant Resources for GEP Implementers

	Source	General inspiration	Recruitment, retention, career progression, and work-life balance	Leadership	Gender in research and knowledge transfer	Gender biases, sexism and sexual harassment
SISTER PROJECTS	Plotina	List of Actions				
	Efforti	Efforti				
	Sage	Sage Toolkit				
	Target	Target GEP Guidelines				
	GEECO		Evaluation standards			
	GARCIA			Gender sensitive mentoring	Working Paper	
	BALTIC GENDER				Tools and resources on gender-sensitive teaching methods in	

⁴ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/step-step-guide>

					higher education	
	GEARING Roles			D.5.1 Repository of inspiring practices on leadership		
OTHER Actors'n initiatives	European Commission		IMPLICIT GENDER BIASES DURING EVALUATIONS HOW TO RAISE AWARENESS AND CHANGE ATTITUDES?			
	University of Aarhus	Gendering in Research (GIR)				
	University of Edinburgh	Equalbite			GenderED	
	EMBO		Exploring Quotas in Academia			
Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory's					CSHL-funded meeting ⁵	
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona					Gender Perspective in Teaching and Research	

When the process of implementation of a GEP is starting in a HEI institution, it is usually useful to provide academic evidences of the impact that these initiatives and strategies might have.

⁵ <https://www.cshl.edu/scientists-take-action-to-prevent-sexual-harassment-and-bias/>

For this purpose, GENDER Action portal of the University of Harvard⁶ provides several examples in different fields of intervention of successful programmes. At the European level, GenPort is also a database of impactful resources⁷ that can help newcomer institutions raising awareness on gender equality issues.

As a subtopic related to recruitment and progression, equal pay has to do with national laws and regulations, but nevertheless some interesting reading relating to pay gaps in the UK⁸ and US⁹ can offer insights into the nationally and institutionally specific environments.

However, the main challenge at hand for most GEP implementing institutions is establishing institutional sex-disaggregated databases, and the GEAR tool¹⁰ provides recommendations on the analytical measures, targets, indicators, monitoring and evaluation that can be used to start to achieve this

Additional insights into gender-sensitive indicators can be found in the database of gender-sensitive indicators used by the Baltic Gender¹¹ project to look at the status of gender equality in its eight partner institutions. This includes:

- A handbook, which has been developed to accompany the data. This contains guidance on the collection of sex-disaggregated data and the calculation of the indicators.
- The data (from November 2017) in XML format in two separate documents; (i) data on the quantitative indicators and (ii) data on the qualitative indicators¹².

Once that data have been collected, HEI might face hindrances to start drafting the GEP documents. In this regard, the progresses made by sister projects such as PLOTINA or EqualIST provide some examples of the GEPs developed with the support of the EU projects. Moreover, PLOTINA provides a template for drafting the GEP and also inspiring examples of actions for each of the axes of the plan.

With regard to challenges related to leadership,¹³ the Gearing-Roles D.5.1. report provides an extensive repository of inspiring initiatives to foster female leadership. In addition, FESTA¹⁴ also offers material to consider, especially for issues concerning organizational change as well as other relevant insights into gender equality in academia.

Another common issue related to gender equality is resistance to quotas in academia.

⁶ <https://gap.hks.harvard.edu/>

⁷ <https://www.genderportal.eu/>

⁸ <https://www.psa.ac.uk/psa/news/why-do-uk-universities-have-such-large-gender-pay-gaps> and <https://www.bbc.com/news/business-47723950>

⁹ <https://www.aeaweb.org/conference/2019/preliminary/paper/Yr24HGdD>

¹⁰ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear>

¹¹ <https://www.baltic-gender.eu/>

¹² <https://www.elsevier.com/connect/gender-and-science-resource-center>

¹³ See also EQUALBITE: <https://www.ed.ac.uk/equality-diversity/innovation-development/equal-bite>

¹⁴ <http://www.festa-europa.eu/>

The EMBO¹⁵ report “Exploring quotas in academia” discusses the use of these, their potential benefits and potential harms. It also presents options for the implementation of specific types of quotas that GEP implementing institutions can benefit from.

For questions concerning research and curricula, the GENDER – NET¹⁶ report can also serve as an inspiration. Baltic Gender also provides tools and resources on gender-sensitive teaching methods in higher education. This resource pack gives an overview of the existing resources, toolkits, and databases on, among other things, gender-sensitive teaching¹⁷ methods in higher education.

Dealing with sexual harassment in academia was also part of previously mentioned PLOTINA project, and some insights can be also found there.

Finally, EFFORTI¹⁸ offers an evaluative approach with regard to gender equality, which GEP implementing institutions can use to evaluate the impact of their actions in this area.

2.3. Recommendations on GEP design process

Based on the contents of institutional reports summarized in D3.1 Assessment report, and the brief PGA reports submitted by each implementing institution, recommendations were elaborated regarding the design process of the GEPs. These recommendations are based both on the respective situations of Gearing-Roles partners and the cumulative experience gained in implementing structural change in research and higher education organisations. They are meant to provide useful guidance to effectively set up a GEP, comprehensively addressing the issues evidenced in above-mentioned reports, and to proceed with its validation at the appropriate institutional level.

Those recommendations are grouped under three titles: a) priority-setting and typology of actions; b) indicators and monitoring and c) GEP drafting and endorsement.

2.3.1. About priority setting

Although operating in different policy contexts, all Gearing-Roles implementing institutions except OBU, are at an early stage of setting up their gender equality agenda. As shown in D3.1,

¹⁵ https://www.embo.org/documents/science_policy/exploring_quotas.pdf

¹⁶ http://www.gender-net.eu/spip.php?article55&lang=en&utm_source=GENDER-NET%20ERA-NET%20report&utm_campaign=4f40296ab4-GENDER_NET_ERA_NET_Reports11_16_2015&utm_medium=email&utm_term=0_c59a655c4d-4f40296ab4-11318921

¹⁷ On teaching, see also: <https://www.genderdiversitylehre.fu-berlin.de/en/toolbox>.

¹⁸ <https://www.efforti.eu/about-efforti>

this entails that some basic work is to be done in areas such as data collection, awareness raising about gender bias and inequalities and internal capacity-building for structural change. As a consequence, identifying priority actions will be of crucial importance for drafting GEPs and ensuring their subsequent implementation. The experience gathered through EU-funded initiatives in this realm, points towards a few criteria that can usefully assist partners in this priority-setting task. It primarily refers to the following notions: windows of opportunities and sustainability, for which a definition is required.

A window of opportunity for structural change is usually understood as the result of circumstances external to the project itself, that are likely to be supportive for (part of) GEP setting up and/or implementation. Those can be of different natures, and typically include:

- The drafting and adoption of a new framework or statutory document at the level of the organization, such as a new statute, a strategic plan for the years ahead, a new mission statement, a document encapsulating the core values of the organization or a training plan.
- A broader transformation process in which the organization can be involved such as a merger, a change affecting its legal entity, a process of internationalization of its recruitment, the adoption of new recruitment and career enhancement processes (such as tenure track) or the pursuit of a certification (such as the HR4R scheme).
- The election or appointment of a new board or rector's team pursuing a gender equality or diversity agenda, or whose agenda could easily accommodate the objectives of gender equality and to integrate a gender perspective in research.

Such windows of opportunity for change can occur at the level of the whole organization or of one of its components (units, faculty, and departments).

Here, sustainability refers to the possibility for each envisioned GEP action to:

- Deliver long-term impact in terms of structural change, as opposed to preparatory steps or short-term actions that might also be required.
- Be embedded into broader existing (or planned) procedures, structures or regulations, such as data collection systems, decision-making procedures, recruitment processes or on-the-job training program. This embeddedness can also be referred as the potential for each planned action to be institutionalized at the level of the organization or of one of its components.

With these two key aspects in mind, GEP actions can be prioritized based on the following drivers:

Emergency:

GEP actions can be prioritized when they intend to remedy a situation clearly evidenced and documented by the audit and which directly affects the functioning of the organization (strong

gender bias in decision-making, non-respect of procedures, ethical or legal regulations...) and/or the work opportunities, the rights or the well-being at work of members of the community, for which immediate or swift action is required.

Efficiency:

GEP actions can also be considered priority on the basis of a principle of efficiency, both in terms of time and resource allocation effectiveness. This is the case when the planned action is relatively easy to deploy immediately, due to available resources, a pre-existing internal demand and/or framework for such action, and a predictably straightforward validation process.

Impact and sustainability:

These are also two relevant drivers for prioritizing GEP actions, anytime a noticeable impact on (part of) the organization can be expected within a relatively short period of time, with predictable positive side-effects on other relevant gender issues. Sustainability will not only be measured in relation to long-lasting impact on the organization, but also on the possibility to embed the action into existing processes, regulations, data collection systems, “ways of doing things” or framework documents of the organization, and to guarantee sufficient resources for their long-term implementation.

Addressing windows of opportunity:

Actions can also be prioritized when specifically addressing windows of opportunity identified at the level of (part of) the organization, in which case they will meet favorable conditions for their implementation, either due to the existence of a broader process of change, to the reshaping of key documents or aspects of the functioning of the organization, to additional resources or simply to the possibility to make converge the GE transformative agenda underlying the GEP with other relevant agendas at the level of the organization. This is the reason why identifying such windows of opportunity is important in the context of GEP design and implementation. While the institutional reports submitted by the partners certainly provide useful insights in that respect, continuous exchanges with key informants might be required to get the full picture and track emerging opportunities so as to frame proposed actions also in relation to identified windows of opportunity for structural change. It should also be acknowledged that GEP actions designed in response to opportunity structures may occasionally include measures of a more symbolic nature, but likely to contribute to further raising awareness on gender related issues or to enhance support for more structural ones.

Typology of actions:

A balance should be found between various types of actions and thematic areas when designing a GEP. With regard to typology, an operational distinction can be made between GEP actions related to further enhancing or deepening diagnosis (data collection, surveys...), those aimed at raising awareness and building internal capacities for change, and those primarily

targeting institutional transformation. As concerns thematic areas, narrowly focusing on those areas for which prior support has been found due to greater awareness can undermine the ability of the GEP to comprehensively address problems at stake and to trigger broader structural change. It is thus quite typical for Gender Equality Plans in research organizations to privilege issues related to human resources' management or work-life balance, while paying less attention to formal and informal decision-making processes, fighting sexual harassment and sexism or integrating the gender dimension in research contents and curricula. Although one or another area can receive more attention on the basis of the diagnosis established at the start of the project, holistic approaches are generally better suited to support organizational change, addressing the full scope of mutually reinforcing bias and inequalities at play.

This holistic dimension of a GEP should be a specific point of attention, as institutional reports summarized in D3.1 tend to show that most partners do not yet fully acknowledge the potential extent of organizational biases, left relatively unaddressed. Relatedly, sexual harassment, everyday sexism and gender-based violence were not identified as potential areas of concern by most partners, possibly indicating that this topic was either marginally addressed (which would warrant efforts towards further analysis) or underestimated. Yet, evidence shows that higher education and research institutions are not immune to sexist language and behaviours nor to some forms of gender-based violence and harassment, and that those can be either facilitated or hampered by organizational culture and practices.

While it is important not to disregard any of the issues highlighted in the baseline assessment, the degree of difficulty posed by often privileged types of actions, such as positive actions or actions towards gender-sensitive communication, should not be underestimated. While the arguments and resistances raised by positive actions are relatively well known, there is a tendency to underestimate the reactions of resistance triggered by gender sensitive communication. Depending on the context and how those actions are framed, they might turn out to be counterproductive as this is a heavily loaded topic to which people tend to react to very strongly, as it affects them deeply and language is part of one's own identity and culture. When such context occurs, it can be recommended to first tackle visual communication in terms of pictures, symbols, colours, subjects, gender balance in terms of authors/speakers/chairs/panels, before addressing (written) language itself (beyond advising inclusive words, where they exist, over the generic masculine).

2.3.2. About indicators and monitoring

It is of utmost importance, at the time of devising future actions on the basis of identified needs, to anticipate that once enacted, these actions will require to be properly monitored. For this purpose, evaluation questions can be devised, so as to anticipate aspects that will require specific monitoring. Although those necessitate to be context specific, a generic set of

evaluation questions for GEP design stage, initially developed for the SUPERA sister project have been included below with the due authorization of the SUPERA consortium.

- Is the design of the GEP based on an in-depth organizational gender analysis? (the mandatory in-depth analysis draws on sufficient data and knowledge)
- Is the GEP based on a clear, context specific strategic framing of issues at stake?
- Does the GEP design involve the contribution or consultation of key stakeholders?
- Is the GEP articulated with existing gender equality strategies or bodies?
- Is the design process sufficiently transparent? (information is communicated to relevant categories of stakeholders, such as social partners, student’s organizations and decision-making bodies of the organization)
- Does the GEP adequately cover the four areas of actions?
- Is it sufficiently holistic not only in terms of issue coverage, but also through addressing people and structures?
- Does the GEP consider intersecting inequalities and disadvantaged groups?
- Are the tasks’ responsibilities formulated and clearly ascribed?

GEP design is also the appropriate timing for reflecting upon SMART and SPICED indicators and thinking ex-ante about how internal monitoring can be organized (and performed).

Below, we provide a specification for such indicators, further commenting on their implementation in the framework of a project as Gearing-Roles.

Table 2: SMART & SPICED Indicators

SMART	SPICED
<p>Specific: Indicators should reflect what the project actually intends to change, avoiding measures that are largely subject to external influences. While planned measures should indeed be within the reach of the organization/project, imminent/planned institutional or policy changes can be taken into account as a plausible scenario conditioning the implementation and outreach of some actions/measures foreseen in the GEP. In which case, a plan B or second level of realization should be foreseen in case those broader changes are not delivered.</p>	<p>Subjective: Informants have a special position or experience that gives them unique insights which may yield a very high return on the investigators’ time. In this sense, what may be seen by others as anecdotal becomes data of critical relevance because of the value of the source.</p>

Measurable: Indicators must be defined precisely so that their measurement and interpretation are not ambiguous. They should provide objective data, independent of whom is collecting the data. They should be comparable across groups and projects, allowing change to be compared and aggregated. Measurability and verifiability yet differ from quantifiability. In other terms, indicators/objectives should always be measurable/verifiable in some way, but not necessarily (and actually, only in a limited number of cases), quantifiable. Measurability and verifiability refer to the possibility to assess whether or not the pursued change did occur, and to which extent, on the basis of qualitative and/or quantitative data. As an example, setting up a pluri-annual gender strategy for recruiting academic staff, based on a baseline assessment of the situation, including a review of recruitment processes, introducing a data monitoring across faculties or units with responsibilities clearly ascribed is measurable, even in the absence of quantitative objectives for Year 1, year 2... (which will make the strategy more efficient and change more quantifiable): the existence of the strategy, the fact it is actually implemented and monitored, that new data is collected, that a certain degree of accountability is introduced and that promised milestones are delivered (or not) is already measurable.

Participatory: Indicators should be, to the greatest possible extent, designed with the contribution of those best placed to assess them. This means involving different categories of stakeholders (such as, in particular, those stakeholders holding the data: HR dept., Scientific Direction...) relevant to the assessment of the indicator or objective, staff and project's beneficiaries.

Attainable: Indicators should be achievable by the project and therefore sensitive to the changes the project intends to make

Interpreted and communicable:
Indicators defined at the level of a unit, a department or a faculty may not mean much

and to its timeline. This is a key aspect since most of (usual) quantitative indicators can hardly be reached within the time frame of a project: unless positive measures are enforced and an important turnover (due to elections...) is foreseen for decision-making positions, little change are to be expected between the enforcement of the GEP and the end of the project. It is even more the case for changing (quantitative) patterns of academic and administrative staff recruitment, which usually involves a number of stakeholders and a variety of (more or less regulated) processes. In this case, changing the qualitative patterns of these appointment and recruitment processes and procedures could be what is to be achieved within the time frame of the project, possibly contemplating a few (modest) milestone quantitative indicators in addition to qualitative ones. Sustainability should also be assessed here: although only part of the objectives of the action will be reasonably attained within the project time frame, introducing specific actions devoted to making it sustainable during the project, will also contribute to make some other objectives predictably attainable beyond the project.

to outsiders. Hence, they should be explained and communicable to other stakeholders.

Relevant: It must be feasible to collect data on the chosen indicators within a reasonable time, at a reasonable cost. Indicators should be directly relevant to the project in question to its overarching objectives. There are a number of aspects making an indicator a relevant one: For instance, whether a planned action is made visible to the community (through

Cross-checked and compared:
The validity of the assessment needs to be cross-checked by comparing different indicators and progress, and by using different informants, methods and researchers.

<p>internal communication), and sustainable (because it is embedded into institutional practice and delivered by/through an already established institutional channel or unit – such as a on the job training dept. for a training measure) make it especially relevant</p>	
<p>Time-bound: Indicators should specify by when a specific change is to be delivered. This timeline is not necessarily a date or specific timeframe but can be associated with / indexed on a predictable institutional milestone (the adoption of a new strategic document, the evaluation of an already existing strategy or plan...). Here also, context matters.</p>	<p>Empowering: The process of setting and assessing indicators should be empowering in itself and allow groups and individuals to reflect critically on their changing situation. This is crucial for different reasons. Among others, because it enhances accountability toward the chosen indicators, improves their intrinsic quality and reliability, lower the level of resistance to data collection or to the objective itself, but also because through participatory regular assessment, new (improved) indicators can be devised, and new issues identified.</p>
	<p>Diverse and aggregated: There should be a deliberate effort to seek out different indicators from a range of groups. This information should be recorded in such a way that these differences can be assessed over time. The objectives/indicators should cover a variety of issues at stake, consider a variety of groups (in terms of position, status, work contract, exposure to intersecting inequalities...). They should also be diverse in balancing quantitative with qualitative aspects, measuring impact and measuring sustainability of change.</p>

Elaborated on the basis of: C. Roche, Impact Assessment for Development Agencies: Learning to Value Change (Oxford: Oxfam/Novib, 1999), pp. 48–49.

2.3.3. About GEP drafting and endorsement

Partners' institutional and PGAs' reports provide key insights for tailoring GEPs.

A first key point is that all partners are in need of pursuing data collection and diagnosis, or strengthening the existing data system, as significant gaps were identified. Those reflect both some difficulties experienced in identifying informants and securing data, and significant room for improvements in institutional data collection and management systems, in particular with regard to the production of sex-disaggregated data. Hence, although to different extents, all GEPs should include actions aimed at:

- Collecting data for the purpose of strengthening the baseline assessment
- Establishing sustainable gender-relevant data collection, analysis and divulgation systems so as to allow adequate periodic monitoring.

This largely common need induces that data collection should serve for periodic reporting and evaluation about GEP and be institutionalized so that it can effectively support the revision of the planned GEP as well as the design of future plans or strategies. Institutional frameworks for such data collection and reporting may already exist and should therefore be identified so as to be expanded to sex-disaggregated data and relevant gender indicators. If such frameworks are not yet in place, it should be considered to establish periodic data collection for the specific purpose of monitoring Gender Equality and assessing GEP implementation. Collected data should be made publicly available.

A second key aspect consists in building capacities for gender mainstreaming in the institution, so that stakeholders such as Human Resources staff or researchers within the frame of their projects, consider gender adequately where relevant. In addition to the activities carried out at consortium level, capacity is also to be built further within the team of change agents to facilitate organizational change. Hence, the training plan to be annexed to the GEP should consider both dimensions.

The last key aspect emerging from D3.1 relates to the sustainability of future GEPs. Under this stream, several points can be raised:

It will be important for partners to build on existing structures, processes, initiatives or resources, rather than setting up all kinds of frameworks from scratch. This is less (project's) resources intensive and more promising in terms of potential for sustainability and the institutionalization of the GEP.

Efforts towards structural change for GE are usually demanding in terms of time and efforts, especially when Gender Equality structures are largely to be built and/or when project core team members do not have full and immediate access to decision-making structures. It is therefore of crucial importance to effectively mobilize the stakeholders and units to engage with the efforts of the project so that change can be delivered and institutionalized. Support from the hierarchy and a clear mandate will be key to ensure this mobilization.

For the same reason, and also for the sake of representativeness and of considering potential intersecting inequalities, it is recommended not to overlook certain groups/categories of stakeholders and to seek collaborations with all of them: notably students, part-time and temporary staff, visiting students and staff, people from gender+ intersecting categories.

Similarly, potential of alliances with external stakeholders, such as regional or national policy makers, gender experts or sister projects should not be neglected. Those (potential) allies should be regularly updated about the project and its achievements, using them as resource persons, involving them in joint actions and using them as leverage on reputation of the institution, so as to enhance internal accountability to the project.

3. Concluding remarks

Recommendations for GEPs provided in this report are envisaged to assist GEP implementing institutions in GEP design and process. The first section draws on the findings of institutional baseline assessments and the D3.1. Report. It presents individual institutions' capacity for addressing gender equality issues and provides common challenges institutions face. Examples of practice, reference points for further inquiry in common issues are provided, based on the knowledge and experience of sister projects and other materials, GEP implementing institutions can use, to assist them for further capacity building in the preparation of their GEP. In the second part, process-specific recommendations are presented to help provide support in terms of strategic planning and sustainability of GEPs.

Nevertheless, efforts to support institutions in the implementation of GEPs will continue through different project activities, of other work packages. GEP implementing institutions can consider using some of these activities (for ex. mentorship programs) to support specific institutional GEP agendas.

